

The Relationship Between Personality Types and Coping Style

by

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This meta-analysis explores the intricate relationship between Big Five personality traits (neuroticism, extraversion, conscientiousness, agreeableness, and openness to experience) and coping mechanisms, with a specific focus on three primary coping styles: task-oriented, emotion-oriented, and avoidance-oriented. Utilizing data obtained from three distinct studies, this analysis synthesizes empirical evidence from diverse cultural and demographic contexts. To establish these results, a variety of personality assessment tools, including the Big Five Inventory (BFI) and NEO Five-Factor Inventory (NEO-FFI), as well as coping strategies questionnaires, such as the Proactive Coping Inventory (PCI), were employed. Findings reveal significant associations between personality traits and specific coping styles. Neuroticism consistently demonstrates a positive correlation with emotion-oriented coping, indicating that individuals scoring high on neuroticism tend to gravitate towards strategies centered on emotional expression and processing. In contrast, conscientiousness is linked to task-oriented coping, suggesting a proactive, solution-focused approach to stressors. These findings have practical implications, informing the development of personalized coping interventions based on individuals' personality assessments. Tailored coping mechanisms, determined from an individual's unique personality profile, hold promise for enhancing mental well-being and resilience in the face of diverse stressors.

Introduction

Stress is a natural component of life and coping with the stress one encounters is crucial to maintaining/improving the state of one's mental health and well-being (Seely, 2018). One factor that can aid as a determinant in the coping process is one's personality type and dominant character traits. According to Seely (2018), personality has been established as a significant predictor of coping strategies. This relationship provides an opportunity to educate individuals on additional ways to cope based on their personality profile. To aid in the exploration of these individualized and personality-specific coping strategies, further research is needed to understand the connection between the five-factor model of personality, also known as the "Big Five" personality traits, and coping styles. By focusing on the Big

Five trait dimensions: neuroticism, extraversion, conscientiousness, agreeableness, and openness, this meta-analysis identifies what adaptive/maladaptive behaviors are practiced in moments of stress by individuals of differing personality types. More importantly, it will discuss how to alter said behaviors to cope both thoroughly and realistically according to one's lifestyle.

Background

The relationship between personality type and coping style is an extensively researched area within psychology, driven by the need to understand how individuals effectively manage stressors for the promotion of mental health and overall well-being. Researchers have delved into various personality dimensions to unravel the nuanced associations with coping styles, seeking patterns that could inform targeted interventions and support strategies. Afshar et al. (2015), Karimizade (2017), and Leszko (2019) share common ground in exploring the intricate connections between personality dimensions and coping styles. Their main commonality lies in their recognition of the Big Five personality model as a foundational framework for understanding personality. Moreover, all three studies highlight the importance of identifying specific coping styles within different personality types. Afshar et al. (2015) investigate coping styles according to stress levels, shedding light on how neuroticism, as a personality trait, influences coping behaviors. Karimizade (2017) focuses on stress coping styles, emphasizing the roles of extraversion and agreeableness in shaping coping mechanisms. Leszko (2019), in the context of prisoners, explores coping styles associated with conscientiousness and openness.

One overarching theme in these studies is the recognition of coping styles as dynamic and context-dependent. They emphasize the need to understand coping strategies within specific populations or stressors, acknowledging the variability in how individuals respond to challenges based on their unique personality profiles. The decision to analyze these three studies in a meta-analysis was done primarily because their data is complementary, contributing to a more

comprehensive understanding of the relationship between personality types and coping mechanisms. By synthesizing the findings and perspectives of Afshar, Karimizade, and Leszko, researchers can identify overarching patterns, commonalities, and potential ways personality traits influence coping across diverse scenarios.

Personality Dimensions: The Big Five Model

The Big Five Inventory (BFI) is a psychological tool designed to assess and measure an individual's personality based on the Big Five personality traits. Utilizing a set of carefully formulated questions, the BFI assesses the key aspects of an individual's behavior, emotions, and cognition. Each question is designed to examine the various facets of personality, aiming to capture the essence of Neuroticism, Extraversion, Conscientiousness, Agreeableness, and Openness to Experience.

Neuroticism

Reflecting the tendency to experience negative emotions such as anxiety, depression, and stress, high neuroticism individuals may exhibit behaviors indicative of emotional volatility and heightened reactivity to stressors (Afshar et al., 2015).

Extraversion

Encompassing sociability, assertiveness, and a tendency to seek external stimulation, individuals with high extraversion levels often exhibit behaviors characterized by outgoingness, enthusiasm, and a proactive approach to engaging with their surroundings (Karimizade, 2017).

Conscientiousness

Organized, responsible, and goal-oriented individuals are often associated with high conscientiousness. They tend to display behaviors associated with meticulous planning, structured task execution, and a strong commitment to achieving their objectives (Leszko, 2019).

Agreeableness

Reflecting an interpersonal orientation, individuals high in agreeableness exhibit behaviors marked by cooperation, empathy, and a positive attitude toward others. Their interactions are often characterized by a collaborative and supportive approach during challenging circumstances (Karimizade, 2017).

Openness

Signifying receptivity to new ideas, creativity, and a preference for novelty, individuals high in openness exhibit behaviors that reflect a curiosity for diverse experiences, innovative thinking, and a willingness to explore unconventional ideas and perspectives (Leszko, 2019).

Categorization of Coping Styles

The general categorization of coping styles into active-coping, emotion-coping, and avoidant coping is a foundational construct widely embraced in psychology. It aids in the organization and comprehension of diverse coping approaches utilized by individuals undergoing challenges.

Task-Oriented

Task-oriented coping involves actively taking steps to address and solve the problems causing stress. Individuals using task-oriented coping focus on practical aspects, seeking solutions, and implementing plans. This may include creating a to-do list, reframing the problem in a more positive light, or being proactive in eliminating the stressor from one's life.

Emotion-Oriented

Emotion-oriented coping centers on managing emotional responses to stress. Instead of directly addressing the source of stress, individuals utilizing this style aim to regulate their emotional reactions and find ways to cope with feelings of distress. For example, they may seek

comfort from friends, engage in activities that bring emotional relief, or express their feelings through creative outlets.

Avoidance-Oriented

Avoidance-oriented coping involves attempting to distance oneself from stressors or the emotions associated with them. Individuals using this style may seek to evade or minimize exposure to stress-inducing situations. More specifically, someone employing avoidance-focused coping might choose to ignore the issue, engage in activities to distract themselves, or physically remove themselves from the stressful situation.

Method

Literature Search

The selection of the three studies was carried out through searches on APA PsychINFO and APA PsychARTICLES, databases for psychological research. Utilizing the key terms "personality and coping," the database searches generated over 20,000 abstracts. The search was refined to only include studies that examined the relationship between personality traits and coping styles. The three distinct studies meet the predetermined criteria, forming the basis for the meta-analysis on personality traits and coping styles across diverse populations and contexts.

Participants and Measures

This research study examines three distinct studies investigating the relationship between personality traits and coping styles across diverse populations and settings. Afshar et al. (2015) explored this association in a general adult population of 4,763 individuals, utilizing a cross-sectional study design. The study population was selected using multistage cluster sampling and convenience sampling in the last stage across 20 cities in Isfahan province. Data collection occurred in two phases, with participants completing self-administered questionnaires on

demographic, lifestyle factors, and psychological variables, yielding a response rate of 86.16%. This approach was facilitated by the use of instruments such as the 12-item General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12), the Big Five Personality Inventory Short Form, and a coping strategies scale. The General Health Questionnaire is a mental health assessment tool that evaluates an individual's psychological well-being across various domains, including depression, anxiety, and overall mental distress. It includes questions related to aspects of well-being, such as the individual's ability to concentrate, sleep patterns, self-esteem, and overall happiness. Moreover, individuals were discerningly categorized into high and low-stress groups based on GHQ-12 criteria, providing an additional layer of insight into the impact of stress on personality and coping. Statistical analyses, including regression, were employed to assess the correlation between personality traits and coping styles based on stress levels.

Karimzade and Besharat (2011) focused on bachelor students, comprising a sample of 300 individuals (150 male, 150 female). Utilizing accessible sampling proportional to enrolled students across all majors, the study investigated the relationship between personality dimensions and stress coping styles. The data collection involved self-administered questionnaires, namely the NEO-FFI personality scale and Tehran Coping Style Scale. The NEO-FFI scale, comprising 60 questions, assessed five key personality dimensions—neuroticism, extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness—utilizing a graded Likert scale. The Tehran Coping Style Scale, comprising 60 questions, assessed three distinct coping styles—problem-focused, positive emotion-focused, and negative emotion-focused—through a four-graded Likert scale.

Leszko et al. (2020) shifted the focus to first-time and recurrent prisoners in Poland. With a sample of 465 incarcerated individuals, the study aimed to understand the relationship between personality traits and coping styles within the context of imprisonment. The participants, aged 18

to 68, were divided into two groups: first-time male inmates (n = 201) and recurrent male inmates (n = 265). Similar to the other studies, self-administered questionnaires were employed in this study. Participants completed the NEO Five Factor Inventory (NEO-FFI), outlined in the Karimzade and Besharat (2011) study. In addition to personality assessment, the coping styles of participants were measured using The Coping Inventory for Stressful Situations (CISS). The CISS comprises three dimensions of coping: avoidance-oriented, emotion-oriented, and task-oriented coping, each measured by 16 items. Statistical analyses, including multiple linear regression, were conducted to explore the correlations between personality traits and coping styles. Despite the differences in populations and settings, all three studies share commonalities in methodological approaches. Self-administered questionnaires and regression analyses were consistently used to assess the associations between personality traits and coping styles.

Results

In investigating the general adult population of the Isfahan province, Afshar et al. (2015) identified neuroticism as a robust predictor of coping style, with negative correlations observed for problem engagement, seeking support, positive reinterpretation, and growth and acceptance, and a positive correlation with avoidance—a pattern indicative of passive coping strategies. Additionally, extraversion, openness, agreeableness, and conscientiousness exhibited positive correlations with problem engagement, seeking support, positive reinterpretation, and growth and acceptance, while displaying negative correlations with avoidance. Furthermore, neuroticism emerged as a risk factor for high-stress levels, while other personality traits, particularly extraversion, served as protective factors. Specifically, extraversion, recognized as the most protective factor (Afshar et al., 2015), demonstrated strong associations with active coping styles and an inclination to seek social support.

Karimzade and Besharat's investigation (2011) delved into the coping dynamics of bachelor students by analyzing personality dimensions as predicting variables and problem-focused, positive emotion-focused, and negative emotion-focused coping styles as criterion variables in regression equations. The study revealed significant findings, particularly in predicting coping styles based on gender. For girls, conscientiousness and extraversion played pivotal roles in determining problem-focused and positive emotion-focused coping styles. Specifically, conscientiousness emerged as a positive predictor for solution-focused coping, while extraversion was associated with heightened positive emotion-focused coping. Additionally, conscientiousness negatively influenced negative emotion-focused coping in girls. In boys, extraversion and openness were identified as significant predictors of positive emotion-focused coping styles, suggesting that individuals with high extraversion and low openness levels tended to employ positive emotion-focused strategies in stressful situations. In contrast, neuroticism and agreeableness were associated with negative emotion-focused coping styles in boys, highlighting that higher neuroticism and lower agreeableness levels correlated with an increased tendency to utilize negative emotion-focused coping strategies in response to stress (Karimzade & Besharat, 2011).

Leszko et al.'s (2020) study uncovered significant associations between age and avoidance coping. The negative association observed between avoidance coping and age underscores an intriguing dynamic, suggesting that, within the prison context, older individuals may be less inclined to employ avoidance strategies when faced with stressors. Task-oriented coping was identified as positively associated with extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness, but negatively associated with neuroticism. Emotion-oriented coping exhibited negative correlations with extraversion, agreeableness, and

conscientiousness, and a positive correlation with neuroticism. Avoidance coping demonstrated a positive association with extraversion and neuroticism. Notably, the correlation analyses between first-time and recurrent inmates revealed consistent patterns across both groups.

Across these studies, a recurring theme emphasizes the importance of considering individual personality traits when observing how people cope in different situations. One key trait, neuroticism, consistently stood out as a key influencer, shaping the nature of coping reactions. High neuroticism scores were linked to coping through emotions, while lower scores were tied to dealing with problems directly. Extraversion consistently correlated with active coping and a tendency to seek support from others. Though not universally explored, conscientiousness hinted at connections with adaptive coping strategies, suggesting its potential importance. The steady link between neuroticism and specific coping styles highlights its broad relevance, making it an essential factor in understanding how people adapt or struggle in coping with stress. This understanding creates a foundation for tailoring stress management approaches, acknowledging the complex connections between distinct personality traits and coping methods across diverse populations and settings.

Discussion

The meta-analysis of studies conducted by Afshar et al. (2015), Karimzade and Besharat (2011), and Leszko et al. (2020) provides a comprehensive examination of the intricate relationship between personality traits and coping styles during moments of stress. Neuroticism consistently emerges as a key determinant, influencing individuals to engage in emotion-focused coping strategies (Afshar et al., 2015; Karimzade & Besharat, 2011). These behaviors may include heightened emotional reactions and a tendency to avoid stressors illustrating maladaptive responses to stress. Extraversion, on the other hand, consistently correlates with active coping

and seeking social support, suggesting adaptive responses to stress (Afshar et al., 2015; Karimzade & Besharat, 2011; Leszko et al., 2020).

Understanding these behaviors is crucial for tailoring interventions that promote effective coping. To alter maladaptive behaviors realistically according to one's lifestyle, interventions should be personalized, considering an individual's unique personality profile. For individuals with high neuroticism, strategies may focus on enhancing problem-focused coping skills and reducing reliance on emotion-focused strategies. Extraverts, with their inclination toward seeking social support, might benefit from interventions that foster and strengthen their social networks. Additionally, individuals with high conscientiousness may derive benefits from deliberately incorporating more emotion-focused coping strategies to complement their well-honed time-management skills and structured problem-solving approach. Individuals scoring high in openness, characterized by creativity and curiosity, might benefit from interventions that encourage diverse coping approaches. Incorporating novel and imaginative behaviors can resonate with their exploratory mindset, fostering adaptability and resilience in the face of stressors. Lastly, individuals with high agreeableness may find interventions centered on enhancing interpersonal communication and conflict resolution skills particularly beneficial. By leveraging their cooperative nature, these individuals can navigate stressors by fostering positive social interactions and collaborative problem-solving.

Future research should investigate the patterns of coping behaviors linked to diverse personality types, considering factors such as age, sex, environmental influences, and individual backgrounds. This exploration should aim to unravel the intricate interplay between personality traits and coping responses within specific contexts. Understanding how cultural and environmental factors shape coping mechanisms will also enrich this area of study and aid in

facilitating the development of tailored interventions. Moreover, a study focused on the relationship between personality types and coping styles, not based on the Big Five trait dimensions, may add another dimension by examining how alternative personality frameworks contribute to the understanding of individual differences in stress responses and coping strategies.

In conclusion, this meta-analysis sheds light on the intricate interplay between personality traits and coping styles, offering valuable insights into the diverse ways individuals navigate stress. The identification of both adaptive and maladaptive behaviors provides a foundation for targeted interventions aimed at empowering individuals to enhance their coping strategies. Recognizing the nuanced relationships between personality traits and coping responses allows for the development of tailored interventions, fostering mental well-being in a variety of populations and settings. This comprehensive understanding contributes to the advancement of strategies that go beyond a one-size-fits-all approach, acknowledging the uniqueness of individuals in managing stress and promoting their overall mental health.

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